

Pharmacomicrobiomics: An Insight to Clinical ApplicationsAcharya TA¹, Chhaiya SB², Mehta DS³¹Professor & Head, Department of Pharmacology, C. U. Shah Medical College, Surendranagar, Gujarat, India²Professor, Department of Pharmacology, C. U. Shah Medical College, Surendranagar, Gujarat, India³Professor & Head, Department of Pharmacology, Swaminarayan Institute of Medical Sciences & Research, Kalol, Gujarat, India

Received: 18-08-2024 / Revised: 21-09-2024 / Accepted: 26-10-2024

Corresponding author: Dr. Acharya TA

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Pharmacomicrobiomics is an emerging branch of Pharmacology, which deals with effect of variations in microbiome on drug related pharmacokinetics and pharmacodynamics. Gut microbes are of numerous types and millions in numbers. Studying alteration of these microbes and its effect on modifying drugs response and disease prognosis has opened many gateways of treatment in many difficult to treat chronic diseases. Cancer, diabetes mellitus, hypertension, rheumatoid arthritis are certain examples of such diseases. Recent advancement like organ-on-chips and bacterial culturomics may allow pharmacomicrobiomics to completely revolutionize the concept of personalized medicine. Present article is about current and possible future clinical applications of pharmacomicrobiomics.

Keywords: Pharmacomicrobiomics, Gut Microbes, Drug-Microbe Interaction, Clinical Applications.

This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Introduction

Pharmacomicrobiomics is defined as effect of variations in microbiome on the drug disposition, action and toxicity.[1,2] The human microbiome project was launched in 2007 with intention of identifying and characterizing collections of human associated microorganisms at multiple anatomical sites and to ascertain influence of these variations on human health and immunity.[2,3] This project laid down the basis of pharmacomicrobiomics.[3] Since then, efforts are being made to understand role of human gut microbes on drug metabolism and how alteration in microbiome flora can alter disease outcome.

Pharmacogenomics concept, which studies genetic analysis of drugs metabolizing enzymes and human genome have not been broadly translated in to clinics.[4] Various studies establishing metabolic capabilities of gut microbes and evolution of microbial genomics from culture based to culture free strategies allowed identification of gut microbe associated with certain disease or with altered drug response.[5] Pharmacomicrobiomics is emerging as an essential component of personalized medicine and modulating the gut microbe has the potential to become a very attractive approach to manage drug efficiency and safety at individual level.[6] Many review articles have been written describing interaction of gut microbe with drug and possible

role of pharmacomicrobiomics in individual disease entity, but it was rare to found article reviewing all the current and possible future clinical applications of pharmacomicrobiomics in single article.

Primary aim of this review is to provide overview of future possibilities of utility of pharmacomicrobiomics in various clinical diseases. Concurrently role of gut microbes in metabolism and drug metabolism has been outlined, but primary focus of this article is to encapsulate clinical applications of pharmacomicrobiomics.

Gut microbes and metabolism

The primary site of drug metabolism is the liver. Drugs are either metabolized by conjugation, reduction, oxidation, isomerization, hydrolysis, or condensation; regardless of the metabolism phases, the aim is to ensure that the drug can be easily excreted.[7] Most drugs are metabolized in two phases. In the first phase, the reactions are mainly about forming a new or modified functional via non-synthetic reactions. The second phase reactions are mainly about conjugating with an endogenous substance in a synthetic reaction such as glucuronic acid, sulfate, or glycine. Synthetic reactions produce water-soluble metabolites that are more easily to be excreted by the kidneys via urine and

by the liver via bile, than those formed in reactions that are non-synthetic.[8]

Orally ingested drugs may pass through the upper GI tract and small intestine into the large intestine, where they encounter the thousands of microbial species that reside in the human gut. Complex drug-microbial interactions occur mainly in the colon. Drugs may change intestinal microenvironment, alter microbial metabolism or affect bacterial growth, thereby altering microbial community composition and function. Conversely, the gut microbiome can also participate directly in chemical transformation of drugs.

Chemical modifications carried out by gut bacteria are very different from these hepatic processes. Gut microbes primarily conduct hydrolytic and reductive reactions to metabolize xenobiotics, while enzymes in the liver typically conduct oxidative and conjugative reactions.[9]

Upon metabolism in the gut and/or the liver, drug metabolites are either transported to targeted tissues or excreted by the kidneys into the urine or by the liver via the biliary system back into the gut lumen. In the gut, drugs or their drug metabolites can be subjected again to bacterial metabolism (e.g., deconjugation) and (re)absorption.[10] These complex reactions and its results can be utilized to modify treatment outcome of various diseases and that is the basic concept behind all the clinical applications of pharmacomicrobiomics.

Clinical Applications

Cancer: In spite of advances in treatment, cancer still remains in difficult to treat zone and carries significant mortality rate. Adverse effects, resistance and unpredictable outcome are the main obstacles in successful treatment of cancer. These obstacles can be overcome by utilizing pharmacomicrobiomics. Microorganism induced modification in drug biotransformation may lead to either increased or decreased bioactivity.[11] There are evidences suggesting beneficial partnership between gut microbiota and anticancer treatment including chemotherapy, radiotherapy, targeted therapy and immunotherapy.[12]

Concomitant administration of probiotics, prebiotics, synbiotics, postbiotics or antibiotics with anticancer treatment can yield added advantages.[13] Significant association has been revealed between gut microbiota and Immune check point inhibitors (ICPIs) which targets programmed cell death protein (PD-1)/programmed cell death ligand (PD-L1) and cytotoxic T lymphocyte associated protein (CTLA-4).[14] These association can be modulated to get favourable outcome in ICPIs. Fecal microbiota transplantation (FMT), probiotics, bacteriophage, minimizing use of antibiotics are some pharmacomicrobiomics strategies to improve outcome of cancer treatment.[15] Potential anticancer drug targets for pharmacomicrobiomics are summarized in Table-1.

Table 1: Correlation between pharmacomicrobiomics and anticancer drugs [12,15-17]:

Anticancer drug	Involved microbes	Modified therapeutic response
Irinotecan	Clostridium clusters	Probiotics can decrease Diarrhoea
5-fluorouracil	Fusobacterium nucleatum	Responsible for resistance
Gemcitabine	Mycoplasma hyorhinis	Responsible for resistance
Cyclophosphamide	Enterococcus hirae, Barnesiella intestinhominis	Responsible for progression free survival
CTLA-4 inhibitors	Bacteroides species	Facilitate antitumor response
PD-1/PDL1 inhibitors	Bifidobacterium species	Facilitate antitumor response
EGFR inhibitors	Commensal skin microbiota	Increased skin toxicity
Oxaliplatin	Ileal microbiota	Facilitate antitumor response
Cisplatin	Unspecified	Responsible for progression free survival
Radiotherapy	Gram positive intestinal flora	Facilitate antitumor response

Metabolic disorders: Gut microbiota and its disturbance also appear to be involved in the pathogenesis of metabolic disorders.[18] Prebiotics promote SCFA (Short Chain Fatty Acid) production and the growth of beneficial bacteria, especially Bifidobacterium and Lactobacillus.[19]

Studies have demonstrated that prebiotic consumption reduces hunger and enhances satiety.[20] This modulation of ingestive behavior is mediated by SCFA-induced changes in gut peptide secretion by promoting Bifidobacterium

populations and prebiotics improve gut barrier function.[21]

Probiotic also shows to improve obesity and metabolic disorders by inhibition of the pathogen adhesion to gut mucosa, stabilization of the microbial community, or improvement of the mucosal integrity and barrier function.[22]

• Diabetes mellitus (DM)

DM type 2 carries major burden of health related issues of modern world. Many treatment options are available to control, but there are still many

problems associated with current treatment options. Interaction of gut microbiota with antidiabetic drugs can play pivotal role in treatment of diabetes.[23] Present scenario of DM and pharmacomicrobiomics can be better understood by three different aspects: 1) various gut microbes play important role in glycemic control by different mechanisms. For example *Roseburia intestinalis* increases insulin sensitivity by increasing IL-22 production; while *Lactobacilli* have acarbose mimetic action by inhibiting alpha glucosidase enzyme.[24] Probiotics containing these organisms can be a potential adjuvant treatment. 2) Current antidiabetic drugs may have interactions with various gut microbes which might be a part of their glucose control mechanism. For example Metformin increases abundance of *Akkermansia muciniphila*, *Bifidobacterium adolescentis*, *Lactobacillus fermentum* etc., which ultimately helps in controlling fasting glucose and HbA1c in DM.[25] Exploring these can give new insight in treatment of diabetes. 3) Interaction of drug with microbiota may be a cause of certain adverse effect. For example Metformin reduces abundance of certain microbes like *Intestinibacter* spp. and *Clostridium* spp., which may contribute to gastrointestinal distress leading to Metformin intolerance.[26] There are preclinical evidence suggesting use of probiotics along with antidiabetic can improve glycemic control in mice.[27] Various clinical trials also have demonstrated antidiabetic role of gut microbes.[24] Administration of probiotics along with antidiabetic drug may be future trend of DM treatment.

Cardiovascular diseases: Cardiovascular diseases are the leading cause of mortality all over the world. Available treatment options have some lacking points which can be fulfilled by pharmacomicrobiomics knowledge. Organisms like *Chlamydia pneumoniae* and *Helicobacter pylori* have been demonstrated to have pivotal role in atherosclerotic heart diseases and acute myocardial infarction.[28,29] Utility of pharmacomicrobiomics in cardiovascular conditions can be rightly explained by example of Digoxin which is an important inotropic drug used in congestive heart failure. Gut bacteria named *Eggethela lenta* reduces digoxin in to inactive metabolite dihydrodigoxin leading to treatment failure in individuals having abundance of this organism.[30] Amino acid arginine, which is important for this organism can also inhibit this inactivation of digoxin.[31] Thus knowledge of pharmacomicrobiomics can alter treatment outcome. Gut microbes produces Trimethylamine-N-oxide (TMAO) from dietary amines such as choline, betaine and L-carnitine, which can be used as biomarker for various cardiovascular conditions.[32]

• Hypertension

Hypertension is a major non-communicable disease and leading cause of cardiovascular diseases.[33] There are numerous types of available treatment options and still new are being invented. In spite of medications 70% patients cannot achieve target BP with single drug.[34] It will be better if natural mechanism can help rather than adding other drugs. Pharmacomicrobiomics can play pivotal role in treatment of hypertension. There are studies showing significant interaction between various antihypertensive drugs like calcium channel blockers, angiotensin receptor blockers, ACE inhibitors and gut microbes.[35] Their interactions can be utilized to modify treatment response. Furthermore certain gut microbes like *Lactobacillus Helveticus*, *Saccharomyces Cerevisiae* and *Lactobacillus Plantarum* have been claimed to reduce blood pressure by themselves.[36,37] Combination of probiotics and antihypertensive drugs might be a future of hypertension treatment.

Depression: Depression is an important CNS disorder and major concern of present generation. Various studies have demonstrated bidirectional interaction between gut microorganisms and CNS activities (e.g. stress, mood, behavior) through immune and neuroendocrine pathway.[38] Abnormal intestinal microbiota leads to a decline in the stability of the gastrointestinal barrier, resulting in an increase of lipopolysaccharide (LPS) entering the body, which activates systemic inflammation and promotes the stress response.[39] However, the treatment of probiotics can effectively prevent intestinal barrier damage and work through multiple mechanisms of action to reduce the response of the HPA axis to stress.[40] It has been demonstrated that the mechanisms of interaction between the gut microbiome and nervous system include: serotonin and tryptophan metabolism, the immune system, gut hormonal response, and short-chain fatty acids from bacterial metabolites.[41] This may provide a new therapeutic idea to enable engineered strains to continuously express therapeutic metabolites after intestinal colonization, so as to achieve therapeutic effects.[42] FMT has shown outstanding results in the treatment of depression.[43] Existing alleviating regimens and antidepressant treatment associated with gut microbes include traditional microbial-targeting drugs, dietary therapy, prebiotics, probiotics, engineered bacteria that express antidepressants, and fecal microbiota transplantation. Acceptable outcomes can be achieved in the prevention and remission of depression by regulating the intestinal microbiota and utilizing the mechanism of action of the gut-brain axis. Moreover, these measures are more flexible and maneuverable, which allows

patients to use non-drug measures to relieve symptoms and improve their quality of life.[44]

Autoimmune disorders

- **Systemic lupus erythematosus (SLE):**

The association between gut microbes and autoimmune disease like SLE is well understood. alteration of microbiome, 'dysbiosis' can induce autoimmune disease in people with certain genetic backgrounds and environmental factors.[45] Gut dysbiosis was partly corrected with FMT, which lead to significant enrichment of SCFAs-producing bacterial taxa and reduction of inflammation-related bacterial taxa, along with reduced levels of IL-6 and CD4+ memory/naïve ratio in the peripheral blood.[46] A mixture of 5 Lactobacillus strains (probiotics) contributed to an anti-inflammatory environment by repairing the gut permeability and decreasing IL-6 and increasing IL-10 production in the gut.[47] Modulation of gut microbiota by eliminating specific bacterial strains or communities with certain antibiotics might represents an alternative approach of microbiota manipulation.[48]

- **Rheumatoid arthritis (RA)**

RA is an immune mediated inflammatory disorder involving joints. In animal models of arthritis, *L. casei* was tested, it showing a decreased incidence of the diseases in association with reduced production of inflammatory cytokines.[49] Similarly in RA patients, supplementation of encapsulated, active *L. casei* induced a reduction of pro-inflammatory cytokines and an increase of anti-inflammatory IL-10, associated with the reduction of the disease activity scores for tender and swollen joints.[50] Another study reported that combined administration of *L. casei*, *L. acidophilus* and *B.bifidum* in capsules was sufficient to reduce the disease activity score; however, tender and swollen joints scores were not decreased.[51]

Administration of both *L. rhamnosus* GR-1 and *L. reuteri* RC-14 in capsules to RA patients in a randomized, double-blind, placebo-controlled clinical trial highlighted a decrease in circulating pro-inflammatory cytokines, although no overall clinical improvement was reported.[52] Combination of anti-inflammatory drugs with microbial targeted approach can be highly beneficial to RA patients.

- **Inflammatory bowel disease**

There is close connection between gut microbiota dysbiosis and the activation of the mucosal immune system in Inflammatory Bowel disease (IBD). Microbe-targeted therapies aimed at restoring gut normobiosis and immune homeostasis are promising therapeutic options.[53] The use of probiotics may modulate dysbiosis in IBD

patients[54], through their strain-specific metabolisms and metabolic by-products[55]. Different strains of *Lactobacillus* and *Bifidobacterium* showed significant capability to reduce pro-inflammatory IL-6 and IL-17 levels.[56] The treatment with a multi-strain probiotics consortium has been shown to possess anti-inflammatory properties in experimental colitis[57] and in different randomized, double-blind, placebo-controlled trials. The use of this probiotics mix in Ulcerative Colitis (UC) patients showed significant effects in terms of clinical remission and clinical response during active UC with no side-effects.[58] Studies showed that therapeutic FMT administered during acute and chronic experimental colitis restores eubiosis and directly modulates both innate and adaptive mucosal immune responses towards the control of intestinal inflammation.[59] FMT not only is able to reduce colonic inflammation, by decreased levels of the pro-inflammatory cytokines, but also initiates the restoration of intestinal homeostasis through the simultaneous activation of different immune-mediated pathways.[59]

Conclusion and future aspects

After considering many of the possible applications it is worthy to say that pharmacomicrobiomics can influence future treatment. Various preclinical and clinical models are being prepared to make path for gut microbes to enter real clinical scenario.[4,60] Recent advances like organ-on-chips and bacterial culturomics which allow to study in-vitro interactions between personalized genome and cultured bacteria can revolutionize field of personal medicine.[6] However, considering complexities of gut microbiota, to make pharmacomicrobiomics a successful strategy, it will require more individualized models and more data bank on microbes and its functions. Definitely there is a huge scope for pharmacomicrobiomics in various burdensome clinical conditions, but extreme hard work at all the levels on invention is required to make this dream come true.

References

1. Dikeocha II, Al-Kabsi AM, Miftahussurur M, Alshawsh MA. Pharmacomicrobiomics: Influence of gut microbiota on drug and xenobiotic metabolism. *Faseb j.* 2022; 36: e22350.
2. Mariam RR, Rama S, Ramy AK. The Human Microbiome Project, Personalized Medicine and the Birth of Pharmacomicrobiomics, *Current Pharmacogenomics and Personalized Medicine* 2010; 8(3).
3. ElRakaiby M, Dutilh BE, Rizkallah MR, Boleij A, Cole JN, Aziz RK. Pharmacomicrobiomics: the impact of human microbiome variations on systems pharma

- cology and personalized therapeutics. *OMICS*. 2014; 18(7):402-14.
4. Guthrie L, Kelly L. Bringing microbiome-drug interaction research into the clinic. *EBioMedicine*. 2019; 44:708-15.
 5. Saad R, Rizkallah MR, Aziz RK. Gut Pharmacomicrobiomics: the tip of an iceberg of complex interactions between drugs and gut-associated microbes. *Gut Pathog*. 2012; 4(1):16.
 6. Doestzada M, Vila AV, Zhernakova A, Koonen DPY, Weersma RK, Touw D et al. Pharmacomicrobiomics: a novel route towards personalized medicine? *Protein Cell*. 2018; 9(5):432-45.
 7. Gratz SW, Duncan G, Richardson AJ. The human fecal microbiota metabolizes deoxynivalenol and deoxynivalenol-3-glucoside and may be responsible for urinary deepoxy-deoxynivalenol. *Appl Environ Microbiol*. 2013; 79(6):1821-25.
 8. Rybak MJ, Le J, Lodise TP, Levine DP, Bradley JS, Liu C et al. Therapeutic monitoring of vancomycin for serious methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* infections: a revised consensus guideline and review by the American Society of Health-System Pharmacists, the Infectious Diseases Society of America, the Pediatric Infectious Diseases Society, and the Society of Infectious Diseases Pharmacists. *Am J Health Syst Pharm*. 2020; 77(11):835-64.
 9. Koppel N, Maini Rekdal V, Balskus EP. Chemical transformation of xenobiotics by the human gut microbiota. *Science*. 2017; 356(6344):eaag2770.
 10. Stein A, Voigt W, Jordan K. Chemotherapy-induced diarrhea: pathophysiology, frequency and guideline-based management. *Ther Adv Med Oncol*. 2010; 2(1):51-63.
 11. Li W, Chen T. An insight to clinical applications of gut microbiota during anticancer therapy. *Advanced Gut & Microbiome Research*. 2022.
 12. Ting NL, Lau HC, Yu J. Cancer pharmacomicrobiomics: targeting microbiota to optimise cancer therapy outcomes. *Gut*. 2022; 71(7):1412-25.
 13. Panebianco C, Andriulli A, Paziienza V. Pharmacomicrobiomics: exploiting the drug-microbiota interactions in anticancer therapies. *Microbiome*. 2018; 6(1):92.
 14. Naqash AR, Kihn-Alarcón AJ, Stavrika C, Kerrigan k, Vareki SM, Pinato DJ et al. The role of gut microbiome in modulating response to immune checkpoint inhibitor therapy in cancer. *Ann Transl Med*. 2021; 9(12):1034.
 15. Huang J, Liu W, Kang W, He Y, Yang R, Mou X et al. Effects of microbiota on anticancer drugs: Current knowledge and potential applications. *EBioMedicine*. 2022; 83:104197.
 16. Vitorino M, Baptista de Almeida S, Alpuim Costa D, Faria A, Calhau C, Azambuja Braga S. Human Microbiota and Immunotherapy in Breast Cancer - A Review of Recent Developments. *Front Oncol*. 2022; 11:815772.
 17. Zhou H, Yuan Y, Wang H, Xiang W, Li S, Zheng H et al. Gut Microbiota: A Potential Target for Cancer Interventions. *Cancer Manag Res*. 2021; 13:8281-96.
 18. Hur KY, Lee MS. Gut Microbiota and Metabolic Disorders. *Diabetes Metab J*. 2015 Jun; 39(3):198-203.
 19. Roberfroid M, Gibson GR, Hoyles L, McCartney AL, Rastall R, Rowland I et al. Prebiotic effects: metabolic and health benefits. *Br J Nutr* 2010; 104 Suppl 2:S1-63.
 20. Cani PD, Lecourt E, Dewulf EM, Sohet FM, Pachikian BD, Naslain D et al. Gut microbiota fermentation of prebiotics increases satietogenic and incretin gut peptide production with consequences for appetite sensation and glucose response after a meal. *Am J Clin Nutr* 2009; 90:1236-43.
 21. Cani PD, Neyrinck AM, Fava F, Knauf C, Burcelin RG, Tuohy KM, Gibson GR, Delzenne NM. Selective increases of bifidobacteria in gut microflora improve high-fat-diet-induced diabetes in mice through a mechanism associated with endotoxaemia. *Diabetologia* 2007; 50:2374-83.
 22. Amar J, Chabo C, Waget A, Klopp P, Vachoux C, Bermudez-Humaran LG et al. Intestinal mucosal adherence and translocation of commensal bacteria at the early onset of type 2 diabetes: molecular mechanisms and probiotic treatment. *EMBO Mol Med* 2011; 3:559-72.
 23. Whang A, Nagpal R, Yadav H. Bi-directional drug-microbiome interactions of anti-diabetics. *EBioMedicine*. 2019; 39:591-602.
 24. Alagiakrishnan K, Halverson T. Holistic perspective of the role of gut microbes in diabetes mellitus and its management. *World J Diabetes*. 2021; 12(9):1463-78.
 25. Chu N, Chan JCN, Chow E. Pharmacomicrobiomics in Western Medicine and Traditional Chinese Medicine in Type 2 Diabetes. *Front. Endocrinol*. 2022; 13:857090.
 26. Adeshirlarijaney A, Gewirtz AT. Considering gut microbiota in treatment of type 2 diabetes mellitus. *Gut Microbes*. 2020; 11(3):253-64.
 27. Stenman LK, Waget A, Garret C, Briand F, Burcelin R, Sulpice T et al. Probiotic B420 and prebiotic polydextrose improve efficacy of antidiabetic drugs in mice. *Diabetol Metab Syndr*. 2015; 7:75.
 28. Spagnoli LG, Pucci S, Bonanno E, Cassone A, Sesti F, Ciervo A et al. Persistent *Chlamydia pneumoniae* infection of cardiomyocytes is

- correlated with fatal myocardial infarction. *Am J Pathol.* 2007; 170(1):33-42.
29. Farsak B, Yildirim A, Akyön Y, Pinar A, Oc M, Boke E et al. Detection of Chlamydia pneumoniae and Helicobacter pylori DNA in human atherosclerotic plaques by PCR. *J Clin Microbiol.* 2000; 38(12):4408-11.
 30. Haiser HJ, Seim KL, Balskus EP, Turnbaugh PJ. Mechanistic insight into digoxin inactivation by *Eggerthella lenta* augments our understanding of its pharmacokinetics. *Gut Microbes.* 2014; 5(2):233-38.
 31. Curini L, Amedei A. Cardiovascular Diseases and Pharmacomicrobiomics: A Perspective on Possible Treatment Relevance. *Biomedicines.* 2021; 9(10):1338.
 32. Papatreou C, Moré M, Bellamine A. Trimethylamine N-Oxide in Relation to Cardiometabolic Health-Cause or Effect?. *Nutrients.* 2020; 12(5):1330.
 33. Mills KT, Stefanescu A, He J. The global epidemiology of hypertension. *Nat Rev Nephrol.* 2020; 16(4):223-37.
 34. Guerrero-García C, Rubio-Guerra AF. Combination therapy in the treatment of hypertension. *Drugs Context.* 2018; 7:212531.
 35. Chen HQ, Gong JY, Xing K, Liu MZ, Ren H, Luo JQ. Pharmacomicrobiomics: Exploiting the Drug-Microbiota Interactions in Antihypertensive Treatment. *Front Med (Lausanne).* 2022; 8:742394.
 36. Hata Y, Yamamoto M, Ohni M, Nakajima K, Nakamura Y, Takano T. A placebo-controlled study of the effect of sour milk on blood pressure in hypertensive subjects. *Am J Clin Nutr.* 1996; 64(5):767-71.
 37. Naruszewicz M, Johansson ML, Zapolska-Downar D, Bukowska H. Effect of *Lactobacillus plantarum* 299v on cardiovascular disease risk factors in smokers. *Am J Clin Nutr.* 2002; 76(6):1249-55.
 38. Kim YK, Shin C. The Microbiota-Gut-Brain Axis in Neuropsychiatric Disorders: Pathophysiological Mechanisms and Novel Treatments. *Curr Neuropharmacol.* 2018; 16(5):559-73.
 39. Velloso LA, Folli F, Saad MJ. TLR4 at the Crossroads of Nutrients, Gut Microbiota, and Metabolic Inflammation. *Endocr Rev.* 2015; 36(3):245-71.
 40. Tillisch K, Labus J, Kilpatrick L, Jiang Z, Stains J, Ebrat B et al. Consumption of fermented milk product with probiotic modulates brain activity. *Gastroenterology.* 2013; 144(7):1394-1401.e14014.
 41. Dash S, Clarke G, Berk M, Jacka FN. The gut microbiome and diet in psychiatry: focus on depression. *Curr Opin Psychiatry.* 2015; 28(1):1-6.
 42. Brown LC, Cockburn CL, Eyre HA. An Introduction to Antidepressant Pharmacomicrobiomics and Implications in Depression. In *Convergence Mental Health: A Transdisciplinary Approach to Innovation*; Oxford University Press: Oxford, UK, 2021; p. 329.
 43. Rao J, Qiao Y, Xie R, Lin L, Jiang J, Wang C et al. Fecal microbiota transplantation ameliorates stress-induced depression-like behaviors associated with the inhibition of glial and NLRP3 inflammasome in rat brain. *J Psychiatr Res.* 2021; 137:147-57.
 44. Zhu F, Tu H, Chen T. The Microbiota-Gut-Brain Axis in Depression: The Potential Pathophysiological Mechanisms and Microbiota Combined Antidepressant Effect. *Nutrients.* 2022; 14(10):2081. Published 2022 May 16.
 45. De Luca F, Shoenfeld Y. The microbiome in autoimmune diseases. *Clin Exp Immunol.* 2019; 195(1):74-85.
 46. Huang C, Yi P, Zhu M, Zhou W, Zhang B, Yi X et al. Safety and efficacy of fecal microbiota transplantation for treatment of systemic lupus erythematosus: An EXPLORER trial. *J Autoimmun.* 2022; 130:102844.
 47. Mu Q, Zhang H, Liao X, Lin K, Liu H, Edwards MR et al. Control of lupus nephritis by changes of gut microbiota. *Microbiome.* 2017; 5:73.
 48. Chen Y, Lin J, Xiao L, Zhang X, Zhao L, Wang M et al. Gut microbiota in systemic lupus erythematosus: A fuse and a solution. *J Autoimmun.* 2022; 132:102867.
 49. Amdekar S, Singh V, Singh R, Sharma P, Keshav P, Kumar A. *Lactobacillus casei* reduces the inflammatory joint damage associated with collagen-induced arthritis (CIA) by reducing the pro-inflammatory cytokines: *Lactobacillus casei*: COX-2 inhibitor. *J Clin Immunol.* 2011; 31(2):147-54.
 50. Vaghef-Mehrabany E, Alipour B, Homayouni-Rad A, Sharif SK, Asghari-Jafarabadi M, Zavvari S. Probiotic supplementation improves inflammatory status in patients with rheumatoid arthritis. *Nutrition.* 2014; 30(4):430-5.
 51. Zamani B, Golkar HR, Farshbaf S, Emadi-Baygi M., Tajabadi-Ebrahimi M., Jafari P et al. Clinical and metabolic response to probiotic supplementation in patients with rheumatoid arthritis: a randomized, double-blind, placebo-controlled trial. *Int J Rheum Dis.* 2016; 19(9):869-79.
 52. Pineda Mde L, Thompson SF, Summers K, de Leon F, Pope J, Reid G. A randomized, double-blinded, placebo-controlled pilot study of probiotics in active rheumatoid

- arthritis. *Med Sci Monit.* 2011; 17(6):CR347-CR354.
53. Strati F, Lattanzi G, Amoroso C, Facciotti F. Microbiota-targeted therapies in inflammation resolution. *Semin Immunol.* 2022; 59:101599.
 54. Wieërs G, Belkhir L, Enaud R, Leclercq S, Philippart de Foy JM, Dequenne I et al. How Probiotics Affect the Microbiota. *Front Cell Infect Microbiol.* 2020; 9:454. Published 2020 Jan 15.
 55. Markowiak P, Ślizewska K. Effects of Probiotics, Prebiotics, and Synbiotics on Human Health. *Nutrients.* 2017; 9(9):1021.
 56. Lim SM, Jang HM, Jang SE, Han MJ, Kim DH. *Lactobacillus fermentum* IM12 attenuates inflammation in mice by inhibiting NF- κ B-STAT3 signalling pathway. *Benef Microbes.* 2017; 8(3):407-19.
 57. De Nitto D, Sarra M, Pallone F, Monteleone G. Interleukin-21 triggers effector cell responses in the gut. *World J Gastroenterol.* 2010; 16(29):3638-41.
 58. Dang X, Xu M, Liu D, Zhou D, Yang W. Assessing the efficacy and safety of fecal microbiota transplantation and probiotic VSL#3 for active ulcerative colitis: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *PLoS One.* 2020; 15(3):e0228846.
 59. Burrello C, Garavaglia F, Cribiù FM, Ercoli G., Lopez G., Troisi J. et al. Therapeutic faecal microbiota transplantation controls intestinal inflammation through IL10 secretion by immune cells. *Nat Commun.* 2018; 9(1):5184.
 60. Steiner, HE, Patterson, HK, Giles, JB, Karnes, JH. Bringing pharmacomicrobiomics to the clinic through well-designed studies. *Clin Transl Sci.* 2022; 15:2303-15.